

**ON THE AVERAGES OF FACTORS OF AN INFINITE WORD ON
A FINITE SET OF INTEGERS**

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Abstract

Given an infinite word $\omega = x_1x_2\cdots$ on a finite set of non-negative integers, and two adjacent *factors* or *blocks* of ω ,

$$A = x_{i+1}x_{i+2}\cdots x_{i+m} \quad \text{and} \quad B = x_{i+m+1}x_{i+m+2}\cdots x_{i+m+n},$$

one can ask whether $A = B$, or whether A is a permutation of B , or whether the *sum* of A , $x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_{i+m}$, equals the sum of B , or whether A, B have the same sum *and* the same length. In this note, we are concerned with whether the *average* of A ,

$$\frac{1}{m}(x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_{i+m}),$$

equals the average of B . (The word 5 4 1 0 1 3 5 1 2 4 2 2 0 3 5 on the alphabet $S = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ contains the three consecutive blocks 0 1 3 5 1, 2, 4 2 2 0, each block having average 2.) Let $\omega = x_1x_2\cdots$, an infinite word on some set of integers, be fixed, and color all the pairs $\{a < b\}$ of non-negative integers by setting

$$f_\omega(a, b) = \frac{1}{b-a}(x_{a+1} + x_{a+2} + \cdots + x_b).$$

Then, applying the canonical Ramsey's theorem to this coloring, we find that there are only two "canonical" colorings rather than the usual four, namely, just the "constant" and "1 - 1" colorings. We study this in detail, for various classes of words. We also give a new and self-contained proof that for every infinite word ω (on a finite set of integers), and every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, ω contains k consecutive blocks all with the same average.

– *Dedicated to the memory of Ron Graham*

1. Introduction

Let $S \subset \mathbb{Z}$, and let $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots$, $x_i \in S$. Thus ω is an infinite word on the alphabet S . Although a number of definitions and results make sense if S is allowed to be infinite (in particular Definitions 1 and 2, and Theorems 1 and 2), in general we restrict ourselves to the case where S is finite.

Here are some simple classes of such words ω :

1. ω is *periodic* if there exist (finite) words y and u with $\omega = yuuu \dots$.
2. ω is *abelian periodic* if there exist words $y, u, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots$ with $\omega = yu_1u_2u_3 \dots$, where each u_i is a permutation of u .
3. ω is *sum periodic* if $\omega = yu_1u_2u_3 \dots$, where all the u_i have the same sum and the same length.
4. ω is *bounded average periodic* if $\omega = yu_1u_2u_3 \dots$, and all the u_i have the same average, and all the lengths of the u_i are bounded by some constant.
5. ω is *average periodic* if $\omega = yu_1u_2u_3 \dots$, and all the u_i have the same average. (Here, the lengths of the u_i are not necessarily bounded.)
6. ω has the *average property*, which means that for all k , ω has a factor $B_1B_2 \dots B_k$, where B_1, B_2, \dots, B_k all have the same average. (Here the lengths of B_1, B_2, \dots, B_k are not necessarily equal.)

It turns out that *every* word ω (on a finite set of integers) has the average property. This is the subject of Section 4.

It is fairly clear that $1 \Rightarrow 2 \Rightarrow 3 \Rightarrow 4 \Rightarrow 5$ and that none of the reverse implications hold. A simple example showing that $5 \not\Rightarrow 4$ is the word $\omega = u_1u_2u_3 \dots$, where $u_n = 0^n1^n0^n$. Thus $\omega = 010001100000111000 \dots$.

The following definition and notation will be used throughout.

Definition 1. Let $\omega = x_1x_2 \dots$ be an infinite word on an alphabet consisting of a finite set of integers. For each such word ω , we define a function f_ω , whose domain is the set of all 2-element subsets of $\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, which we denote in the usual way by $[\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}]^2$. Given $a, b \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, a < b$, we write $f_\omega(a, b)$ instead of $f_\omega(\{a, b\})$, and we define, for $u = x_{a+1}x_{a+2} \dots x_b$, $f_\omega(u) = f_\omega(a, b) = \text{average of } \{x_{a+1}, x_{a+2}, \dots, x_b\} = \frac{1}{b-a}(x_{a+1} + x_{a+2} + \dots + x_b)$.

Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots$, where each $x_i \in S$, S a finite set of integers, we will often be concerned with whether or not

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} f_\omega(0, j) = \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{j}(x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_j)$$

exists.

Let ω be a given infinite word, on a finite set of integers. In Section 2 we apply the canonical Ramsey’s theorem to the coloring f_ω of $[\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}]^2$, and we find that there is an infinite subset I of $\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ such that f_ω restricted to $[I]^2$ is either constant or $1 - 1$.

Definition 2. Let $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots$, where each $x_i \in S$, S a finite set of integers. If there is an infinite subset I of $\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ such that f_ω restricted to $[I]^2$ is constant, we say that f_ω has the *constant property*. If there is an infinite subset I of $\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ such that f_ω restricted to $[I]^2$ is $1 - 1$, we say that f_ω has the *$1 - 1$ property*.

We completely characterize f_ω (in terms of whether f_ω has the constant property or the $1 - 1$ property or both), whenever ω is not average periodic, or is average periodic but not bounded average periodic, or is bounded average periodic.

Somewhat surprisingly, it turns out that if ω is not average periodic, then the sequence $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ must converge as $i \rightarrow \infty$.

We summarize the results of Section 2 in Section 3.

Then, in Section 4, we show that *every* infinite word ω (on a finite set S of integers) has the *average property* (#6 on the previous list). This fact was conjectured by the second author in the late 1970s. A proof did not appear until 2012 [1]. That proof relied on the existence of many collinear points in certain sequences of planar lattice points [7]. The present proof is self-contained and makes no reference to lattice points; however, the method was inspired by Peter L. Montgomery’s proof [5] of the existence of many collinear points in certain sequences of lattice points. (Namely, any sequence $\{P_n\}$ where for all $n \geq 0, P_{n+1} - P_n \in \{(0, 1), (1, 0)\}$.)

Section 5 has a few remarks on collinear points in the plane.

In Section 6, we show that it would be enough, in Section 4, to prove the main result only for the case $S = \{0, 1\}$.

2. The Canonical Version of Ramsey’s Theorem for the Coloring f_ω

The following lemma is crucial.

Lemma 1. *Let $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots, x_i \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $f_\omega(a, b)$ defined as in Definition 1. If $a, b, c \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, a < b < c$, and any two of $f_\omega(a, b), f_\omega(b, c), f_\omega(a, c)$ are equal, then all three are equal.*

Proof. The proof is a simple computation. □

Theorem 1. *Let $\omega = x_1x_2 \dots$ be an infinite word on an alphabet consisting of a finite set of integers. Then, referring to Definitions 1 and 2, f_ω has the constant property, or the $1 - 1$ property, or both.*

Proof. Applying the ordinary canonical Ramsey’s theorem (see, for example, [4], Section 5) to this coloring tells us that there exists an infinite subset I of $\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ such that f_ω restricted to $[I]^2$ is one of:

1. 1 – 1 or
2. “min”: $f_\omega(a, b) = f_\omega(c, d)$ iff $a = c$ (for all $a, b, c, d \in I, a < b, c < d$) or
3. “max”: $f_\omega(a, b) = f_\omega(c, d)$ iff $b = d$ (for all $a, b, c, d \in I, a < b, c < d$) or
4. constant.

Now let $a, b, c \in I$, where $a < b < c$. If f_ω restricted to $[I]^2$ is the “min” coloring, then $f_\omega(a, b) = f_\omega(a, c)$. Then, by Lemma 1, $f_\omega(a, b) = f_\omega(b, c) = f_\omega(a, c)$. Since f_ω is the “min” coloring, $f_\omega(a, c) \neq f_\omega(b, c)$, a contradiction. Similarly, f_ω restricted to $[I]^2$ cannot be the “max” coloring. \square

Lemma 2. *Given ω , an infinite word on some finite set of integers, if*

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f_\omega(0, i) = \alpha \in \mathbb{R},$$

then, for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f_\omega(m, i) = \alpha$.

Proof. It’s easy to see that for each fixed $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} |f_\omega(0, i) - f_\omega(m, i)| = 0$. \square

Theorem 2. *If $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots$, $x_i \in S \subset \mathbb{Z}$, S finite, is not average periodic, then f_ω has the 1 – 1 property, but does not have the constant property.*

Proof. (For the definition of “average periodic,” see the beginning of the Introduction.) According to Theorem 1, f_ω has at least one of the two properties. But f_ω cannot have the constant property, since if $I = \{i_1 < i_2 < i_3 < \dots\}$ and f_ω is constant on $[I]^2$, then in particular $f_\omega(i_1, i_2) = f_\omega(i_2, i_3) = \dots$. Setting

$$y = x_1x_2 \dots x_{i_1}, u_1 = x_{i_1+1}x_{i_1+2} \dots x_{i_2}, u_2 = x_{i_2+1}x_{i_2+2} \dots x_{i_3}, \dots,$$

we have $\omega = yu_1u_2u_3 \dots$ and u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots all have the same average, i.e., ω is average periodic. \square

Remark 1. If $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots$, $x_i \in S$, S finite, a simple calculation shows that

$$|f_\omega(0, n) - f_\omega(0, n + 1)| \leq \frac{1}{n + 1}(\max S - \min S).$$

Remark 2. For any such ω , the sequence $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}_{i=1}^\infty$, being a bounded sequence, has one or more limit points.

Theorem 3. *Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \dots$, $x_i \in S$, S finite, assume that for some set $D = \{j_1 < j_2 < j_3 < \dots\}$ and real number α ,*

$$f_\omega(0, j_i) \rightarrow \alpha \text{ as } i \rightarrow \infty.$$

Then the following two statements are equivalent.

- (a) There is an infinite set $A \subset D$ such that for all $s, t \in A, s < t, f_\omega(s, t) \neq \alpha$.
- (b) There is an infinite set $B \subset D$ such that f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[B]^2$.

Proof. First we show (a) \Rightarrow (b). To simplify the notation, we might as well assume that $D = \mathbb{N}$, that is, we assume that $f_\omega(0, i) \rightarrow \alpha$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$ and, for all $s, t \in \mathbb{N}, s < t, f_\omega(s, t) \neq \alpha$. We now choose the set $B = \{k_1 < k_2 < k_3 < \dots\}$ inductively as follows.

Set $k_1 = 1, k_2 = 2$. If $k_1 < k_2 < \dots < k_n$ have been chosen so that f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[\{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n\}]^2$, then choose $k_{n+1} > k_n$ so that for each $r, 1 \leq r \leq n$,

$$0 < |\alpha - f_\omega(k_r, k_{n+1})| < \min\{|\alpha - f_\omega(k_u, k_v)| : 1 \leq u < v \leq n\}.$$

(This is possible by Lemma 2: for each $r, 1 \leq r \leq n, f_\omega(k_r, i) \rightarrow \alpha$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$.)

Thus we automatically have that for all $1 \leq u < v \leq n, 1 \leq r \leq n$,

$$f_\omega(k_u, k_v) \neq f_\omega(k_r, k_{n+1}). \tag{1}$$

It remains to show that

$$1 \leq r < s \leq n \Rightarrow f_\omega(k_r, k_{n+1}) \neq f_\omega(k_s, k_{n+1}).$$

But if $1 \leq r < s \leq n$ (and hence $k_r < k_s < k_{n+1}$), the equality $f_\omega(k_r, k_{n+1}) = f_\omega(k_s, k_{n+1})$ implies by Lemma 1 that $f_\omega(k_r, k_s) = f_\omega(k_s, k_{n+1})$, contradicting (from the definition of k_{n+1}) the inequality (1) above.

To show that (b) \Rightarrow (a), simply note that if f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[B]^2$, then $f_\omega(s, t) = \alpha$ can hold for at most one pair s, t in B . Hence $B - \{s, t\}$ can serve as A . \square

Corollary 1. *Let A be any infinite subset of \mathbb{N} with asymptotic density 0, and let ω be the characteristic sequence of A . Then there is an infinite subset B of \mathbb{N} such that f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[B]^2$.*

Lemma 3. *Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3\dots, x_i \in S \subset \mathbb{Z}, S$ finite, such that $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ does not converge, then there are minimum and maximum limit points $L_1 < L_2$. Furthermore, any real number $r, L_1 < r < L_2$, is also a limit point of $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$.*

Proof. Clearly the infimum L_1 and the supremum L_2 of the set of limit points are also limit points. Let $L_1 < r < L_2$. Let $\epsilon > 0$. For infinitely many n , we have $f_\omega(0, n) < r \leq f_\omega(0, n + 1)$. For large n , by Remark 1,

$$f_\omega(0, n + 1) - f_\omega(0, n) < \epsilon.$$

Hence, $|r - f_\omega(0, n)| < \epsilon$ for infinitely many n . \square

Example. Consider the binary word $\omega = 0^1 1^2 0^3 1^4 0^5 1^6 \dots$. By induction,

$$2! + 4! + 6! + \dots + (2n)! < 2 \cdot (2n)!,$$

thus

$$f_\omega(0, 1! + 2! + 3! + \dots + (2n + 1)!) = \frac{2! + 4! + 6! + \dots + (2n)!}{1! + 2! + 3! + \dots + (2n + 1)!} < \frac{2}{2n + 1} \rightarrow 0.$$

Similarly,

$$1! + 3! + 5! + \dots + (2n - 1)! < 2 \cdot (2n - 1)!,$$

and thus

$$f_\omega(0, 1! + 2! + 3! + \dots + (2n)!) = 1 - \frac{1! + 3! + 5! + \dots + (2n - 1)!}{1! + 2! + 3! + \dots + (2n)!} > 1 - \frac{2}{2n} \rightarrow 1.$$

Thus every real number in $[0, 1]$ is a limit point of $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$.

Theorem 4. Let $\omega = x_1 x_2 x_3 \dots$ (on a finite alphabet $S \subset \mathbb{Z}$) be such that $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ does not converge. Then f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[B]^2$ for some infinite subset B of \mathbb{N} .

Proof. Using Lemma 3, choose an irrational number α and a sequence $D = \{j_1 < j_2 < j_3 < \dots\}$ such that

$$f_\omega(0, j_i) \rightarrow \alpha \text{ as } i \rightarrow \infty.$$

Since $f_\omega(r, s)$ is always rational, and hence unequal to α , Theorem 3 gives us an infinite subset B of D such that f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[B]^2$. \square

Remark 3. We will see in Theorem 6 that when $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ does not converge, then f_ω also has the constant property in a very strong sense.

Let $\omega = x_1 x_2 x_3 \dots$ be such that the sequence $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ converges. We now give a condition on such words ω which is equivalent to the statement that the coloring f_ω has the 1 – 1 property.

Definition 3. Given ω (on a finite alphabet $S \subset \mathbb{Z}$) such that the sequence $f_\omega(0, i) \rightarrow \alpha$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$, the equivalence relation \mathbf{E} on \mathbb{N} is defined as follows.

$$a \cong b \text{ if and only if } a = b \text{ or } a \neq b \text{ and } f_\omega(\min\{a, b\}, \max\{a, b\}) = \alpha.$$

Note that the transitivity property of the relation \cong follows from Lemma 1.

Theorem 5. Let $\omega = x_1 x_2 x_3 \dots$ (on a finite alphabet $S \subset \mathbb{Z}$) and assume $f_\omega(0, i) \rightarrow \alpha$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$. Then the following two statements are equivalent.

- (a) The coloring, f_ω , has the 1 – 1 property.
- (b) The number of equivalence classes produced by \mathbf{E} is infinite.

Proof. First we show that (b) implies (a). Assume the number of equivalence classes of \mathbf{E} is infinite. Let A consist of one element from each equivalence class. Clearly $i, j \in A \Rightarrow f_\omega(i, j) \neq \alpha$, so by Theorem 3, f_ω is 1 – 1 on $[B]^2$, where B is some infinite subset of A .

Now we show that (not b) implies (not a). Let A be any infinite subset of \mathbb{N} . Let $r, s, t \in A, r < s < t$, where $r \cong s \cong t$. Then $f_\omega(r, s) = \alpha = f_\omega(s, t)$, so f_ω is not 1 – 1 on $[A]^2$. Thus f_ω does not have the 1 – 1 property. \square

Corollary 2. *If $\omega = yu_1u_2u_3 \cdots$ (each $f_\omega(u_i) = \alpha$) is bounded average periodic, then f_ω has the constant property, but not the 1 – 1 property.*

Proof. We must have $f_\omega(0, i) \rightarrow \alpha$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$. But the number of equivalence classes produced by \mathbf{E} must be finite, for if i and j are in the same position in two equal u_k , then they will be in the same class. Hence an upper bound for the number of classes is $|y| + RT$, where R is the number of different u_k and T is an upper bound for the lengths of the u_k . \square

Theorem 6. *Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \cdots$ (where each $x_i \in S, S$ a finite set of integers), suppose $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ does not converge as $i \rightarrow \infty$. Then ω is average periodic. In fact, if α is any rational number with $L_1 < \alpha < L_2$ (where L_1 and L_2 are the minimum and maximum limit points of $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$), then there is an infinite set $A \subset \mathbb{N}$ such that, if $i, j \in A, i < j$, then $f_\omega(i, j) = \alpha$.*

Proof. Recall that for $0 \leq i < j, f_\omega(i, j) = (x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + x_{i+3} + \cdots + x_j)/(j - i)$. We will use the notation $g(n) = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \cdots + x_n = nf_\omega(0, n)$.

Let $\alpha = P/Q$. We know that there are infinitely many n such that

$$f_\omega(0, n) \leq P/Q < f_\omega(0, n + 1).$$

Using $nf_\omega(0, n) = g(n)$, the left and right hand inequalities become, respectively, $Qg(n) \leq Pn$ and $(n + 1)P < Qg(n + 1)$.

Now $g(n + 1) = g(n) + x_{n+1}$, so the right hand side becomes $P + Pn < Qx_{n+1} + Qg(n)$. Since $Qg(n) \leq Pn$, we have

$$P + Pn < Qx_{n+1} + Qg(n) \leq Qx_{n+1} + Pn,$$

or, subtracting $P + Pn$,

$$0 < (Qx_{n+1} - P) + (Qg(n) - Pn) \leq Qx_{n+1} - P \leq Q(\max S) - P. \tag{2}$$

The x_{n+1} vary with n , but since S is finite, there will be infinitely many n such that (2) holds with each x_{n+1} being the same (say each $x_{n+1} = a$). Among these values of n , since the integers $(Qa - P) + (Qg(n) - Pn)$ are bounded above and

below, there is an infinite set A on which they are all equal. For any two elements of A , say $i < j$, subtracting gives

$$0 = (Qa - P) + Qg(j) - Pj - ((Qa - P) + Qg(i) - Pi) = Q(g(j) - g(i)) - P(j - i),$$

or $P(j - i) = Q(g(j) - g(i))$, and finally $\alpha = P/Q = \frac{g(j)-g(i)}{j-i} =$

$$\frac{(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_j) - (x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_i)}{j - i} = \frac{x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \dots + x_j}{j - i} = f_\omega(i, j).$$

□

3. Summary of Section 2

Here is a summary of our results so far. According to Theorem 2 and Theorem 6, if ω is not average periodic then $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ converges and f_ω has only the 1-1 property. According to Corollary 2, if ω is bounded average periodic, then $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ converges and f_ω has only the constant property. Theorems 4, 5, 6 fill in the remaining parts of the diagram below.

4. The Average Property

We now show (Theorem 7 below) that every infinite word $\omega = x_1x_2x_3\cdots$, where each $x_i \in S, S$ a finite set of integers, has the average property. That is, ω has arbitrarily long sequences of consecutive blocks, all with the same average.

Lemma 4. *Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3\cdots$ (where each $x_i \in S, S$ a finite set of integers), let $k \geq 2$, and suppose that ω does not contain k consecutive blocks with equal averages. Let $g(n) = x_1 + x_2 + \cdots + x_n = nf_\omega(0, n)$ and $h(n) = Qg(n) - Pn$, where $P \geq 0$ and $Q > 0$ are integers. Let c be any integer. Then $h(n) = c$ for at most k positive integers n .*

Proof. Suppose $h(n_i) = c$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k + 1$. Then $g(n_i) = (h(n_i) + Pn_i)/Q = (c + Pn_i)/Q$ and

$$f_\omega(n_i, n_{i+1}) = \frac{g(n_{i+1}) - g(n_i)}{n_{i+1} - n_i} = \frac{c + Pn_{i+1} - c - Pn_i}{Q(n_{i+1} - n_i)} = P/Q.$$

Thus ω has k consecutive blocks with equal averages, a contradiction. □

Lemma 5. *Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3\cdots$ (where each $x_i \in S, S$ a finite set of integers), let $k \geq 2$, and suppose that ω does not contain k consecutive blocks with equal averages. Let $g(n) = x_1 + x_2 + \cdots + x_n = nf_\omega(0, n)$ and $h(n) = Qg(n) - Pn$, where $P \geq 0$ and $Q > 0$ are integers. Then, for any $m > 0$, there exists $n \in [1, (2m + 1)k + 1]$ such that*

$$|f_\omega(0, n) - P/Q| > \frac{1}{2kQ}.$$

Proof. For any $c \in [-m, m]$, by the previous Lemma, at most k values of n are such that $h(n) = c$. Hence there are at most $(2m + 1)k$ values of n such that $h(n) \in [-m, m]$. Hence there must be $n \in [1, (2m + 1)k + 1]$ such that $h(n) \notin [-m, m]$ and for this n we must have $|h(n)| > m$. Hence, $|f_\omega(0, n) - P/Q| = |g(n)/n - P/Q| =$

$$\left| \frac{Qg(n) - Pn}{Qn} \right| = \left| \frac{h(n)}{Qn} \right| \geq \frac{m + 1}{Q((2m + 1)k + 1)} > \frac{1}{2kQ}.$$

□

Lemma 6. *Given $\omega = x_1x_2x_3\cdots$ (where each $x_i \in S, S$ a finite set of integers), let $k \geq 2$, and suppose that ω does not contain k consecutive blocks with equal averages. Let $P \geq 0$ and $Q > 0$ be integers. Then there exists an ascending sequence $n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \cdots$ such that for each i ,*

$$|f_\omega(0, n_i) - P/Q| > 1/2kQ. \tag{3}$$

Proof. Let $m > 0$. By the previous lemma, there is an $n_1 \in [1, (2m + 1)k + 1]$ such that $|h(n_1)| > m$ such that (3) holds with $i = 1$. Now let

$$m' = \max\{|h(t)| : t \in [1, (2m + 1)k + 1]\}.$$

Clearly $m' > m$ and there exists an $n_2 \in [1, (2m' + 1)k + 1]$ such that $|h(n_2)| > m'$ and (3) holds with $i = 2$. We must have $n_2 \in [1, (2m' + 1)k + 1] \setminus [1, (2m + 1)k + 1]$, so that

$$n_1 < n_2.$$

The argument can be repeated with $m'' = \max\{|h(t)| : t \in [1, (2m' + 1)k + 1]\}$ to obtain $n_3 > n_2$, etc., with each n_i satisfying (3). \square

In Theorem 7 below, we will use the well known result from approximation theory that, if L is any real and $M > 0$, then there exists a rational number P/Q such that $Q > M$ and

$$\left|L - \frac{P}{Q}\right| < \frac{1}{2Q^2}. \tag{4}$$

Theorem 7. *Every infinite word $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \cdots$ (where each $x_i \in S$, S a finite set of integers) contains M consecutive equal average blocks for any $M > 0$.*

Proof. If $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ does not converge, then Theorem 6 shows that ω has, in fact, an infinite sequence of equal average consecutive blocks.

If $f_\omega(0, i) \rightarrow L$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$, assume ω does not have k consecutive blocks of equal average. We choose $P \geq 0$ and $Q > k$ such that (4) holds. Lemma 6 gives us an infinite set of indices,

$$n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \cdots$$

such that (3) holds for each i . Note that $|f_\omega(0, n_i) - P/Q| > 1/2kQ > 1/2Q^2 > |L - P/Q|$, so that

$$\left|f_\omega(0, n_i) - \frac{P}{Q}\right| - \left|L - \frac{P}{Q}\right| > \frac{1}{2kQ} - \frac{1}{2Q^2} = \epsilon > 0.$$

Hence, for each i ,

$$\left|f_\omega(0, n_i) - L\right| = \left|\left(f_\omega(0, n_i) - \frac{P}{Q}\right) - \left(L - \frac{P}{Q}\right)\right| \geq \left|f_\omega(0, n_i) - \frac{P}{Q}\right| - \left|L - \frac{P}{Q}\right| > \epsilon.$$

This implies that $\{f_\omega(0, i)\}$ has a limit point other than L , a contradiction. \square

5. Remarks on Collinear Planar Lattice Points

Let $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \cdots$ (where each $x_i \in S$, S a finite set of integers). Define a sequence of plane lattice points $\mathbf{P} = \{P_i\}_{i=0}^\infty$ by setting

$$P_0 = (0, 0), \quad P_{i+1} - P_i = (1, x_{i+1}), i \geq 0,$$

so that $P_n = (n, x_1 + \dots + x_n)$. Now let $m < n < q$. Then P_m, P_n, P_q are collinear exactly when the slope of the line through P_m, P_n equals the slope of the line through P_n, P_q , that is, exactly when

$$\frac{1}{n - m}((x_1 + \dots + x_n) - (x_1 + \dots + x_m)) = \frac{1}{q - m}((x_1 + \dots + x_q) - (x_1 + \dots + x_n)),$$

or

$$\frac{1}{n - m}(x_{m+1} + \dots + x_n) = \frac{1}{q - m}(x_{n+1} + \dots + x_q),$$

or

$$f_\omega(m, n) = f_\omega(n, q).$$

Thus the sequence $\{P_i\}$ contains $M + 1$ collinear points iff the word ω contains M consecutive equal average blocks, for any $M > 0$.

A more general class of sequences $\{P_i\}$ of planar points is obtained by specifying a set A of planar points and then requiring $P_0 = (0, 0), P_{i+1} - P_i \in A, i \geq 0$. Such sequences are considered in [2], [3], [5], [6], [7].

6. $S = \{0, 1\}$ Suffices

One version of van der Waerden’s famous theorem on arithmetic progressions [8] is this: given any infinite word ω on a finite set of positive integers, and any k , there are k consecutive blocks in ω all having the same *sum*.

To see that this statement is implied by van der Waerden’s theorem, let $\omega = x_1x_2x_3\dots$, where each $x_i \in S$, S a finite subset of \mathbb{N} , and let $T = \{t_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$, where $t_i = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_i, i \geq 1$. Since $t_{i+1} - t_i \leq \max S$, a finite number of translates of T covers \mathbb{N} . Removing elements in overlapping translates, we obtain a finite coloring of \mathbb{N} , hence by van der Waerden’s theorem, there are arbitrarily large monochromatic arithmetic progressions. Each monochromatic arithmetic progression is a subset of a translate of T , hence T itself contains arbitrarily large arithmetic progressions. If, for example, t_5, t_9, t_{18} , are in arithmetic progression, then $(x_1 + \dots + x_9) - (x_1 + \dots + x_5) = (x_1 + \dots + x_{18}) - (x_1 + \dots + x_9)$, or $x_6 + x_7 + x_8 + x_9 = x_{10} + \dots + x_{18}$.

The above statement seems similar in spirit to the equal average property, which says: given any infinite word ω on a finite set of positive integers, and any k , there are k consecutive blocks in ω all having the same *average*.

The usual version of van der Waerden’s theorem is that if \mathbb{N} is finitely colored, there are arbitrarily large (finite) monochromatic arithmetic progressions. It is well known that it suffices to show this for just the case of two colors.

We now show (Theorem 9) that to prove that any infinite word on a finite set S of integers has the average property, it suffices to show this just for the case $S = \{0, 1\}$.

First we give a somewhat easier result.

Theorem 8. *Assume that every infinite word on $\{0, 1\}$ has the average property. Let $\{P\}_{i=0}^\infty$ be any sequence of points in the plane such that $P_i - P_{i-1} \in \{(0, 1), (1, 0)\}$, $i \geq 1$. Then $\{P\}_{i=0}^\infty$ contains k collinear points for every k .*

Proof. Let $P(0, 0) = (0, 0)$ and, for $i \geq 1$, $P_i - P_{i-1} \in \{(0, 1), (1, 0)\}$. For $i \geq 1$, define

$$x_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } P_i - P_{i-1} = (0, 1) \\ 0, & \text{if } P_i - P_{i-1} = (1, 0) \end{cases}$$

and let $\omega = x_1x_2x_3 \cdots$. Let $i < j < k$, where

$$x_{i+1}x_{i+2} \cdots x_j, \quad x_{j+1}x_{j+2} \cdots x_k$$

have the same average. In the first block, $x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j$ is the number of ones in the block, that is, the number of vertical (unit) steps made from P_i to P_j . Also, $(j - i) - (x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j)$ is the number of zeros in $x_{i+1}x_{i+2} \cdots x_j$, that is, the number of horizontal (unit) steps made from P_i to P_j . Hence

$$\frac{x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j}{(j - i) - (x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j)}$$

is the slope of the line connecting P_i to P_j . Replacing i, j by j, k , the same expression gives the slope of the line connecting P_j to P_k .

But

$$\frac{x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j}{j - i} = \frac{x_{j+1} + x_{j+2} + \cdots + x_k}{k - j}$$

(the two blocks have the same average), hence, since

$$\frac{a}{b} = \frac{c}{d} \quad \text{if and only if} \quad \frac{a}{b - a} = \frac{c}{d - c},$$

we have finally

$$\frac{x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j}{(j - i) - (x_{i+1} + x_{i+2} + \cdots + x_j)} = \frac{x_{j+1} + x_{j+2} + \cdots + x_k}{(k - j) - (x_{j+1} + x_{j+2} + \cdots + x_k)}.$$

□

The above argument is reversible, so the converse of Theorem 8 is also true.

Theorem 9. *Assume that every infinite word on $\{0, 1\}$ has the average property. Then every infinite word on any finite set S of integers has the average property.*

Proof. Let

$$\omega = y_1y_2y_3 \cdots$$

be an infinite word on a finite set S of non-negative integers. (The more general case, allowing S to be a finite set of integers, follows by subtracting a suitable positive integer from each y_i , which does not disturb the average property.)

For each i , let $u_i = 1^{y_i}0$. For example, if $y_i = 3$, then $u_i = 1110$. If $y_i = 0$, we set $u_i = 0$.

Let

$$\beta = u_1u_2u_3 \cdots = x_1x_2x_3 \cdots, \quad x_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \geq 1.$$

By assumption, for any $M > 0$, β has M consecutive blocks

$$x_{t_1+1}x_{t_1+2} \cdots x_{t_2}, x_{t_2+1}x_{t_2+2} \cdots x_{t_3}, \quad \cdots, \quad x_{t_M+1}x_{t_M+2} \cdots x_{t_{M+1}}$$

each with the same average, and we wish to show that ω has K consecutive blocks with equal averages, for any K .

Let K be given. Since each x_{t_i} occurs in some u_j , and there are only finitely many distinct u_j , if we choose M large enough, we can find $K + 1$ indices amongst the t_i , say

$$j_1 < j_2 < j_3 < \cdots < j_{K+1},$$

such that each x_{j_i} occurs in the *same position* of the *same block* u ($u \in \{1^a0 \mid a \in S\}$). By Lemma 1, the K blocks

$$x_{j_1+1}x_{j_1+2} \cdots x_{j_2}, x_{j_2+1}x_{j_2+2} \cdots x_{j_3}, \quad \cdots, \quad x_{j_K+1}x_{j_K+2} \cdots x_{j_{K+1}},$$

also have the same average.

From these K blocks, let us consider two that are adjacent. To ease the notation, let $f = j_i, g = j_{i+1}$, and $h = j_{i+2}$. We must have, for the two consecutive blocks in β determined by f, g , and h , two corresponding consecutive blocks in ω . Precisely, we have

$$x_{f+1}x_{f+2} \cdots x_g = ru_{m+1}u_{m+2} \cdots u_{n-1}s \quad (\text{corresponding to } y_{m+1}y_{m+2} \cdots y_n)$$

and

$$x_{g+1}x_{g+2} \cdots x_h = ru_{n+1}u_{n+2} \cdots u_{p-1}s \quad (\text{corresponding to } y_{n+1}y_{n+2} \cdots y_p)$$

for appropriate m, n , and p , and words r and s , where $sr = u = u_m = u_n = u_p$ (r will be the empty word, in the case $x_f = x_g = x_h = 0$.)

Summing these blocks, we get (using $\sum r + \sum s = \sum u_n$)

$$\begin{aligned} x_{f+1} + x_{f+2} + \cdots + x_g &= \sum r + \sum u_{m+1} + \sum u_{m+2} + \cdots + \sum u_{n-1} + \sum s \\ &= \sum u_{m+1} + \sum u_{m+2} + \cdots + \sum u_{n-1} + \sum u_n = y_{m+1} + y_{m+2} + \cdots + y_n, \end{aligned}$$

and, similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} x_{g+1} + x_{g+2} + \cdots + x_h &= \sum r + \sum u_{n+1} + \sum u_{n+2} + \cdots + \sum u_{p-1} + \sum s \\ &= \sum u_{n+1} + \sum u_{n+2} + \cdots + \sum u_{p-1} + \sum u_p = y_{n+1} + y_{n+2} + \cdots + y_p. \end{aligned}$$

Now, in the blocks $x_{f+1}x_{f+2} \cdots x_g$ and $x_{g+1}x_{g+2} \cdots x_h$, the numbers of 1s are

$$x_{f+1} + x_{f+2} + \cdots + x_g \text{ and } x_{g+1} + x_{g+2} + \cdots + x_h$$

respectively and the numbers of 0s are $n - m$ and $p - n$, respectively, since each u_i , as well as sr , contains exactly one 0. Hence,

$$g - f = (n - m) + x_{f+1} + x_{f+2} + \cdots + x_g$$

and

$$h - g = (p - n) + x_{g+1} + x_{g+2} + \cdots + x_h.$$

The blocks $x_{f+1}x_{f+2} \cdots x_g$ and $x_{g+1}x_{g+2} \cdots x_h$ have the same average, so

$$\frac{x_{f+1} + x_{f+2} + x_{f+3} + \cdots + x_g}{(n - m) + x_{f+1} + x_{f+2} + x_{f+3} + \cdots + x_g} = \frac{x_{g+1} + x_{g+2} + x_{g+3} + \cdots + x_h}{(p - n) + x_{g+1} + x_{g+2} + x_{g+3} + \cdots + x_h}.$$

Since $a/b = c/d$ if and only if $a/(b + a) = c/(d + c)$, we get

$$\frac{x_{f+1} + x_{f+2} + x_{f+3} + \cdots + x_g}{(n - m)} = \frac{x_{g+1} + x_{g+2} + x_{g+3} + \cdots + x_h}{(p - n)};$$

that is,

$$\frac{y_{m+1} + y_{m+2} + y_{m+3} + \cdots + y_n}{(n - m)} = \frac{y_{n+1} + y_{n+2} + y_{n+3} + \cdots + y_p}{(p - n)}.$$

□

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